

Studies in the Synthesis of Xanthone Derivatives : Part II. Synthesis of Furoxanthenes

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7-Allyl-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (Ia), on treatment with osmium tetroxide-potassium periodate, followed by cyclization with polyphosphoric acid afforded 5-methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro (2',3'-6,7) xanthone (II), which on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal gave 4-methylfuro (3',2'-2,3) xanthone (III). It was also synthesised from 2-allyl-3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone (IVa) by carrying out oxidation with osmium tetroxide-potassium periodate, and cyclization with PPA. Similarly furo (2',3'-3,4) xanthone (VI), was synthesised, starting from 5-allyl-6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (Ic), and also from 4-allyl-3-hydroxyxanthone(IVb).

THE synthesis of furoxanthone, unsubstituted in furan ring was generally achieved by internal Claisen condensation¹ of the aldehyde ester derivative or by ozonolysis² of the *o*-hydroxyallylxanthone, followed by cyclization with polyphosphoric acid. Sesbadi and coworkers³ obtained *o*-hydroxyacetaldehyde derivatives, in good yield by oxidation with osmium tetroxide. We adopted the same method³, for the synthesis, of two furoxanthenes, viz. 4-methylfuro(3',2'-2,3)xanthone(III) and furo(2',3'-3,4)xanthone¹ (VI), each was synthesised starting from two different types of *o*-hydroxyallylxanthenes.

7-allyl-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroxanthone(Ia), prepared as described in part-1⁴ of the series, was subjected to oxidation with osmium tetroxide-potassium periodate in ethyl acetate-water to give corresponding 7-acetaldehyde derivative, which in next step cyclized to 5-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrofuro-(2',3'-6,7) xanthone(II), with PPA. This on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal (10%), in boiling diphenyl ether afforded 4-methylfuro(3', 2'-2, 3)xanthone(III). It was also synthesised, by the reaction of osmium tetroxide potassium-periodate on 2-allyl-3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone (IVa), in ethyl acetate-water followed by cyclization of resulting intermediate with PPA.

(Ia) R = CH₃, R₁ = OH, R₂ = -CH₂ - CH = CH₂

(Ib) R = CH₃, R₁ = OH, R₂ = -CH₂ - CHO

(Ic) R = -CH₂ - CH = CH₂, R₁ = OH, R₂ = H

Similarly 5-allyl-6-hydroxy-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroxanthone (Ic)⁴ was converted to 1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro (3',2'-5,6)xanthone(V), by carrying out oxidation with osmium tetroxide-potassium periodate and cyclization with PPA. The compound(V), on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal in boiling diphenyl ether gave furo-(2',3'-3,4)xanthone(VI). It was also synthesised from 4-allyl-3-hydroxyxanthone (IVb)⁴, with the step-wise use of osmium tetroxide-potassium periodate and PPA.

(II)

(III)

(IVa) R = -CH₂ - CH = CH₂, R₁ = OH, R₂ = -CH₃

(IVb) R = H, R₁ = OH, R₂ = -CH₂ - CH = CH₂

Experimental

¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer R-32 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. IR spectra were determined on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. UV spectra were recorded on Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer.

7-Acetaldehyde-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroxanthone(1b) :

7-Allyl-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroxanthone (0.8 g) in ethyl acetate (230 ml) and osmium tetroxide (70 mg) in water (80 ml) were vigorously stirred for 15 minutes. Potassium periodate (1.8 g) was added in small quantities to the dark solution over a period of 90 minutes. The reaction mixture was stirred 2 hr. more. The acetate layer was separated, washed with water, dried with sodium sulphate and concentrated. The residue left, was dissolved in chloroform and the clear solution was percolated through a short column of alumina. It was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 267°, yield 0.3g. Found: C, 70.71, H, 6.18. C₁₆H₁₆O₄ requires: C, 70.58, H, 5.88%. IR spectrum (nujol): 1630 cm⁻¹ (γ-pyronyl>C=O), 1680 cm⁻¹ (-CHO), and a broad band at 3350 cm⁻¹ (-OH).

5-Methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro(2',3'-6,7)xanthone(II):

7-Acetaldehyde-6-hydroxy-5-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroxanthone (0.25 g) was treated with PPA (12 ml) in an oil bath at 110° for 2 hr. It was then poured into ice water. The solid separated was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and finally with water. It crystallised from benzene as fine small needles, m.p. 206°, yield 0.12 g. (Found: C, 75.19, H, 5.51. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ requires: C, 75.55, H, 5.50%). IR spectrum (nujol): 870 cm⁻¹ (furan ring), 1640 cm⁻¹ (γ-pyronyl>C=O); UV λ_{Max}^{chloroform}: 246 nm (log e 4.74), 278 nm (log e 4.6⁰); NMR CDCl₃: δ 1.57-2.03 (4H, m, C₂-H₂ and C₃-H₂), 2.55 (3H, s, C₅-CH₃), 2.40-2.80 (4H, m, C₁-H₂ and C₄-H₂), 6.82 (1H, d, J=2.2 Hz, C₄-H), 7.68 (1H, d, J=2.2 Hz, C₆-H), 8.25 (1H, s, C₈-H).

4-Methylfuro(3',2'-2,3)xanthone(III) :

5-Methyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro(2',3'-6,7)-xanthone (0.6 g) and palladised charcoal (10%, 0.8 g) were taken in diphenyl ether (10 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 10 hr. It was then filtered hot and the solvent was removed by steam distillation. The remaining residue was extracted with ethyl acetate, concentrated and chromatographed on silica gel. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (1:9) gave the product, which was crystallised from benzene as small needles m.p. 216°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 76.37; H, 3.87. C₁₆H₁₀O₃ requires: C, 76.81; H, 4.00%). NMR (CDCl₃): δ 2.71 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 6.89 (1H, d, J=2Hz, C₄-H), 7.30-7.68 (3H, m, C₅-H, C₆-H and C₇-H), 7.75 (1H, d, J=2Hz, C₅-H), 8.32 (1H, d, J=10Hz C₈-H), 8.38 (1H, s, C₁-H).

2-Allyl-3-hydroxy-4-methylxanthone (0.5 g) in ethyl acetate (200 ml) and osmium tetroxide (65 mg) in water (70 ml) were vigorously stirred for 15 minutes. Potassium periodate (2 g) was added in small quantities as in case of 1b). The intermediate 5-acetaldehyde product was treated with PPA (15 ml) for 3 hr. at 120°, to give III (0.13 g). It crystallised from benzene as small needles, m.p. 216° (Found: C, 77.21; H, 4.36. C₁₆H₁₀O₃ requires: C, 76.81; H, 4.00%). The mixed m.p. with previously obtained product was not depressed.

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydrofuro (3',2'-5,6) xanthone(V) :

5-Allyl-6-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroxanthone (0.7 g) in ethyl acetate (180 ml) and osmium tetroxide (50 mg) in water (70 ml) were vigorously stirred for 20 minutes. Potassium periodate (1.5 g) was added in small quantities (as in case of 1b). The intermediate 5-acetaldehyde product was treated with PPA (15 ml) for 4 hr. at 130° to give V (160 mg). It crystallised from benzene as fine needles, m.p. 205°. (Found: C, 74.85; H, 4.82. C₁₅H₁₂O₃ requires: C, 75.00; H, 5.00%). NMR (CDCl₃): δ 1.60-2.50 (4H, m, C₂-H₂ and C₃-H₂), 2.48-2.82 (4H, m, C₁-H₂ and C₄-H₂), 7.08 (1H, d, J=2.2Hz, C₄-H), 7.46 (1H, d, J=10 Hz C₇-H), 7.70 (1H, d, J=2.2 Hz, C₆-H), 8.15 (1H, d, J=10Hz, C₈-H).

Furo (2',3'-3',4) xanthone(VI) :

1,2,3,4-tetrahydrofuro (3',2'-5,6) xanthone (0.25 g) and palladised charcoal (0.5 g) were refluxed in diphenyl ether (10 ml) for 12 hr. The reaction mixture worked up as usual gave IV (0.1 g). It crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. 191° (lit¹, m.p. 192°). (Found: C, 75.86; H, 3.56. C₁₅H₈O₃ requires C, 76.28; H, 3.39%). NMR (CDCl₃): δ 7.10 (1H, d, J=2Hz, C₄-H), 7.28-7.68 (4H, m, C₂-H, C₅-H, C₆-H and C₇-H), 7.75 (1H, d, J=2Hz, C₆-H), 8.19 (1H, d, J=10Hz, C₈-H), 8.28 (1H, d, J=10Hz, C₁-H).

4-Allyl-3-hydroxyxanthone (0.5 g) and osmium tetroxide (40mg) were dissolved in ethyl acetate (200 ml) and water (50 ml). Potassium periodate (1.2 g) was added as usual. The intermediate 4-acetaldehyde product, thus obtained was taken in PPA (12 ml) and heated at 130° for 3 hr. to give furo (2',3'-3,4) xanthone (VI) (0.12 g). It crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. 191°. The mixed m.p. with previously obtained product was not depressed.

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